

Threats to *Himchari* National Park of Bangladesh: An Integrated Conservation Approach

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Abstract

The *Himchari* National Park was highly rich in floral diversity and acted as a greenbelt against tropical cyclones in the coastal areas of Bangladesh. The park has been degraded severely and now consists of isolated patches of trees, and is primarily dominated by scattered scrub vegetation. Therefore, the study aimed to identify the factors causing the degradation. Based on empirical data collected through personal interviews and focus group discussions, it was revealed that conversion of forest land, clearing and level of hills, rampant over-exploitation of the forest resources, overload of tourism, Rohingya flux, exotic plantations and ineffective ecomanagement were identified as the main causal factors of the degradation. An integrated conservation approach was developed with the help of the respondents considering the local ground.

Keywords: *Himchari* National Park, Habitat destruction, overexploitation, Asian Elephant, Hill destruction, *Rohingya* flux

Introduction

Himchari National Park (HNP) is located in the southeastern part of Bangladesh consisting of 1729 ha. It is a very important conservation area due to its proximity to the tourist city *Cox's Bazar*. It is also a part of *Cox's Bazar-Teknaf* Peninsula Reserved Forest, which offers the scenic beauty of green hills and blue sea waves. The park was established in 1980 comprising the reserve and protected forest areas of *Bhangamera*, *Chainda* and *Jhilongja* blocks under *Cox's Bazar* Forest Department. It borders the Bay of Bengal and represents remnants of a few hilly semi-evergreen tropical forest patches. The park is managed under five small administrative units locally known as bits. They are *Kolatoli*, *Himchari*, *Jhilongja*, Link Road and *Chainda* bit. Once upon a time, this ever-green tropical forest was a passage for Asian Elephants (Sukumar 1992; Rabbi 2017). The natural beauty of the area provides a welcome break from the hustle and bustle of city life, for locals as well as tourists. More than two million visitors come here each year for recreational activities, picnics, hunting, sunbath and bird watching (Hassan & Shahnewaz 2014). It is a paradise for bird watchers (Rabbi 2017). It is a transitional ground for the fauna of the Indo-Himalayan and Indo-Malayan ecological sub-regions, which provides breeding areas for some globally-threatened species of fauna (Sarker *et al.* 2021; Rashid 2019).

The park was highly rich in floral diversity (Hossen & Hossain 2018; Hossen *et al.* 2021). The forest cover acts as a greenbelt against tropical cyclones in the coastal areas (Rahman 2023a). Different studies reported that this park has been degraded severely (Salam *et al.* 1999; Islam *et al.* 2022; Hossen *et al.* 2021). Habitat degradation is the main threat to achieving sustainability and green growth in Bangladesh (Rahman 2023 i, j). The forest now consists of isolated patches of trees and is primarily dominated by scattered scrub vegetation (Gain, 2002). Therefore, the study aimed to identify the factors and causes of the degradation.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The secondary data were collected from different sources of literature. Three focus group discussions were done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders in three blocks. A total number of 30 respondents were personally interviewed with a semi-structured questionnaire. Based on the respondents' the threats to habitats were identified. The respondents also help to frame an integrated conservation approach. Content analysis was done to interpret the data.

Threats to conservation

Conversion of forest lands

The respondents informed that the conversion of forest land into croplands is the prime cause of the degradation. Betel leaf cultivation increased in that area drastically. Consequently, the chance of natural regeneration and succession of the forest vegetation disappeared from the converted land. Rice monoculture expanded in the comparatively lower land, which degraded the agrobiodiversity as well. The respondents added that the conversion of forestland occurs for constructing homes, infrastructure, tourist cottages, roads, etc. The respondents pointed out that this conversion increased the Asian Elephant-Human conflict. The conversion of forestland renders the system inhospitable for the natural regeneration and growth of wild plant associates, causing a net loss in floral diversity (Rahman *et al.* 2007; 2009; Raman & Vacik 2009; Rahman 2023b, h). On the other hand, Rice monoculture decreases the abundance of honeybees, bats, and birds (Rahman 2023c). Different studies support the intensified human-elephant conflict in this park (Sukumar 1992; Santiapillai & Jackson 1990; Larsen & Cormack 2017; Olivier 1978; Chowdhury *et al.* 2014; Chowdhury & Izumiyama 2014; Rashid 2019).

Clearing hills

The respondents admitted that the land grabbers and the influential people of the societies are involved in clearing hills in this area. They noted that cutting or levelling of the hills accompanied by the removal of remaining vegetation coverage from hills is also a major cause of forest degradation, erosion and landslides. As a result, this area experiences degradation of the natural ecosystem, various natural disasters, huge land erosion, soil infertility and unusual flash floods. High demand from the tourism industry, estate business, brick kiln and human settlement are the prime factors that work behind the hill clearing. The hill clearing tarnishes the natural habitats of the flora and fauna and generates an onslaught of environmental hazards (Hassan *et al.* 2015).

Rampant illicit logging and over-exploitation of forest resources

The respondents argued that over-exploitation of forest resources like illicit logging, encroachment, indiscriminate harvesting of tree species and non-timber forest products degrade this natural habitat. They added that poaching, expansion of settlement, unemployment, easy

accessibility to the forest, easy mobility, lack of patrolling; vegetable collection and sand extraction are fueling these over-exploitations. The over-extraction of forest resources endangered the flora of this park (Hossen & Hossain 2018).

Over tourism

The respondents added that tourism in this park is gradually increasing year by year, which hampers natural regeneration due to the continuous human movements. The overload of tourists includes camping and walking, which crushes, shears off and uproots vegetation cover. Tourism impacts vegetation through loss of height, biomass, and reproductive structures (Rahman & Vacik 2009). It also decreases humus level, nutrient supply, pH values and electrical conductivity, and contrarily increases soil compactness (Rahman & Vacik 2009).

Exotic Plantations and Invasions

The respondents argued the plantation of the fast-growing timbering exotic tree species in the degraded land suppresses the natural vegetation and natural regeneration. Hossen & Hossain (2018) reported that the introduction of exotic tree species degraded the natural ecosystem of this park. The exotic species degrades soil health, alters the habitat substantially for native flora and fauna, spreads pests and pathogens and facilitates biological invasion in the natural habitats (Rahman 2023 e, f). The respondents noted that due to the absence of mother trees no natural regeneration occurs, which facilitates the invasion of sun grass. The canopy opening increases resource availability for invaders (Rahman 2023d).

Forest Dwellers

The respondents admitted that many local people live in the forests and they are dependent on the forest resources for their livelihood. They cut seedlings and saplings of trees for fuelwood. They collect deadwood and litter for fuelwood. Removal of deadwood causes degradation of bird's habitat (Rahman 2023g).

Rohingya flux

The respondents opined that the forest degradation is propelled by the unplanned settlement of Rohingya refugees. They are destructing forest coverage and skewing the passages of the Asian

Elephants. Consequently, the elephant-human conflicts have increased in recent days. Islam *et al.* (2022) reported a significant portion of forest cover disappeared after the arrival of the Rohingya refugee. The elephant-human has been intensified in the recent time due to anthropogenic disturbances caused by the refugee (Mukul *et al.* 2019; Rahman 2019; Hassan *et al.* 2018; Mowla & Hossain 2021; Taufiq 2021, Barua *et al.* 2018; Quader *et al.* 2018).

Ineffective co-management

The respondents opined that the key positions of the co-management committees are occupied by the degraders. Consequently, co-management does not work. The same findings were reported from other parts of the country (Rahman 2021 a, b; Rahman 2022 a, b; Rahman & Islam 2018).

Integrated Conservation Approach

Based on the respondents' perceptions, the following measures can be taken to conserve biodiversity and minimize human disturbances:

- ✓ Declaring the park as a transnational ecosystem for plant and wildlife
- ✓ Strictly Prohibiting clear felling
- ✓ Strictly prohibiting extraction of rare species
- ✓ Motivating the people living not only inside the park but also in the buffer zone, forest edges and adjacent areas
- ✓ Promoting local people in the conservation programme
- ✓ Forestation in the degraded and fallow space by the native plant species
- ✓ Mapping and monitoring of the biological resources
- ✓ Establishing an information system to track the level of biodiversity
- ✓ Initiating ex-situ conservation of the endangered species
- ✓ Promoting public awareness through different print, electronic and social media
- ✓ Raising funds for conservation programmes from local sources
- ✓ Restoring natural cover
- ✓ Maintaining at least two canopy layers in the buffer zone
- ✓ Planting mixed canopy tree species suitable for this area
- ✓ Planting large diameter trees with strong root systems to provide critical structure for the habitat of some animals and to prevent chronic erosion of beach

- ✓ Strengthening research and development
- ✓ Halting the introduction of invasive species
- ✓ Gap-filling by rare tree species
- ✓ Promoting natural regeneration
- ✓ Protecting natural regenerations
- ✓ Establishing gene banks to conserve the gene pool of endangered species
- ✓ Adopting alternative income generation for local stakeholders
- ✓ Promoting ecotourism
- ✓ Sharing the conservation plan with the communities in pivotal areas
- ✓ Controlling the number of tourists
- ✓ Enforcing laws to conserve the hills
- ✓ Reducing human population growth in forests
- ✓ Introducing a biological corridor
- ✓ Promoting natural succession
- ✓ Taking effective actions against encroachers and land grabbers
- ✓ Taking appropriate actions against animal poaching
- ✓ Alleviating poverty in the adjacent areas of forests
- ✓ Exploring alternative fuel sources in the forest and adjacent areas
- ✓ Controlling animal grazing

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